

LAKBAY-DIWA ✦
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME I ISSUE VIII

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

DECEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VIII (December 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

JOEMALIN M. CUBALIT, MAENGL

Graduate Studies Student

Baguio Central University

Baguio, Benguet, CAR, Philippines

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17939331

R.E.A.D.: Sustaining Literature in the Age of Digital Distraction

Growing up in the Cordillera, I often saw the dap-ay as more than a circle of stones. Up until now, it plays central in a community, where elders and young ones gathered at the end of the day, warming themselves by the fire and exchange stories about the past and talk about the present. Children listen quietly, learning not from books, but from the voices of those who came before them. In more traditional times, this was where the elderly would educate the children with stories about their own heroes and ancestors.

Moments spend surrounding the Dap-ay have produced literatures such as short stories, folktales and riddles. These literatures developed the mental abilities and creative imagination of the elders were passed on from one generation to another generation. They were published for the learning and enjoyment of the children. The so called batang 90s and generation X somehow have enjoyed reading literary books. They proudly share the stories about Tiririt, Henny Penny, Minda and Linda and Pugad Lawin which they claim that such amazing literary memories is the result of spending time in reading.

In my ten years of teaching high school students, reading problems became noticeable, and my biggest realization, at least for me, is the need to correct and improve the reading habits of my students. But classrooms these days cannot compete with distractions caused by gadgets. Students are more drawn to videos and visuals with sounds, than into sitting down to read for more than a few minutes. As a result, I notice that many students falter when it comes to reading. They often feel uneasy, or show no interest. Even though they try to finish, it is hard for them to truly understand the material. Furthermore, the 2018 PISA findings, which placed Filipino learners at the bottom in reading literacy did not surprise me. At that time, I was already seeing similar results among English students who took PHIL-IRI exams (OECD,2019; OECD,2023).

This decline in reading skills is not just a national issue. It is also a personal one that teachers like me face every single day inside the classroom. As an English teacher in a public school, I witness how reading habits have drastically changed. There are times when my students read a passage smoothly, but when I ask, "What does it mean?" or "What do you think happens afterward?", the room becomes silent or that they become uncertain. They can summarize a story, but explaining why events happened or what comes next is often difficult for them.

While this situation is concerning, I still find hope when I see genuine interest among students, especially when sparks of curiosity, imagination, and empathy are tapped. As educators, parents, and members of a reading community, it is our shared responsibility to nurture these sparks and help them grow into lifelong flames of literacy.

To respond to this challenge, I hold on to one simple yet powerful acronym that guides my personal and professional advocacy: R.E.A.D. – Reclaim, Engage, Appreciate, and Dedicate.

R – Reclaim the Love for Reading

Reclaiming reading means restoring its rightful place in our lives, not as an academic requirement, but as a meaningful part of being human. Literature should not feel like an obligation but an opportunity: to pause, to feel, and to understand.

In my English class, we revisit timeless Filipino stories like *The Centipede* or *Footnote to Youth*. I encourage my students to look beyond the plot and connect the story to their own experiences. We ask: What would you have done differently if you were the character? What lesson does this story hold for your generation? These discussions transform reading into reflection, making it personal and alive.

Reclaiming the love for reading also means creating spaces in the classroom where books are accessible, dedicating time during homeroom periods, and encouraging storytelling after recess. I applaud the city government of Baguio and the Baguio City Library who started a reading corner at Burnham Park. This encourages everyone to engage again to reading.

E – Engage Learners through Meaningful and Modern Ways

Digital technology can be a partner of literacy. It is often blamed for the decline in reading, but I believe it can be used creatively and purposefully.

In the school, my students use digital tools to breathe life into literature. They design visual-text posters for key passages, record monologues from a character’s point of view, or create short “book reels” that summarize literary themes. The Department of Education (DepEd) challenges the teachers to be innovators in teaching reading.

While I use technological tools like TV, laptop, and even cellphones for e-books/articles as alternatives to support reading comprehension, I am also mindful not to replace the basic reading and understanding that comes from the printed texts. It bridges the gap between traditional literature and 21st century learners, transforming the classroom into a space where reading becomes dynamic, collaborative and relevant.

Beyond the classroom, I also bring this engagement home. My husband and I make it a point to read with our children. We visit bookstores and libraries together, allowing them to choose their books, sometimes comics, sometimes novels, sometimes poetry. We ask them to share what they've read during family time. Their eyes light up when they talk about a story's twist or a poem's rhythm. In those moments, I am reminded that reading is not taught, it is shared.

A – Appreciate the Power of Literature in Real Life

Reading literature is more than learning words, it is learning life. It may sound a cliché but it is true that every story offers readers a window to the world and a mirror to the soul. In class, when my students read about characters who face loss, courage, or injustice, I see them begin to empathize. They realize that the struggles of literary characters reflect the real emotions and dilemmas they face. A story about friendship teaches loyalty. A novel about resilience teaches perseverance. Literature connects them to human experiences beyond their own, helping them understand and manage their own emotions.

This appreciation also has a social impact. When we read about inequality, corruption, or environmental neglect, students begin to form opinions and take stands. Reading becomes a quiet form of civic education, training young minds to analyze, question, and act with compassion.

With growing discussions on mental health awareness, I see literature as therapy. It provides comfort, clarity, and connection. Through poetry, stories, and drama, readers learn to articulate feelings that are otherwise difficult to express. Literature helps heal and humanize.

D – Dedicate Time and Effort to Build a Reading Culture

Sustaining the love for literature requires dedication, steady, intentional, and shared. Teachers must lead the way. When students see us carrying books, reading aloud with enthusiasm, or protecting time for silent reading, they realize that reading is not just for school, it is a way of life.

In the school, we have started small reading initiatives during English Month and National Reading Month, such as "Drop Everything and Read" or DEAR, and classroom "Reading Corners." But these should not end after celebrations. The challenge is to make reading part of the school's culture year-round.

I also believe that parents play a crucial role. In my own home, we limit gadget time and schedule "reading hours." Even ten minutes before bedtime can make a difference. Modeling the behavior is more powerful than a hundred reminders. Children mirror what they see, when they see us read, they will follow.

The statistics on literacy may seem discouraging, but they are not final. Every teacher who reads a story aloud, every parent who opens a book beside a child, every student who

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VIII (December 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

chooses to finish a chapter instead of scrolling endlessly, all of them are quiet victories for literacy.

When we Reclaim, Engage, Appreciate, and Dedicate, we do more than teach reading, we nurture thinkers, dreamers, and doers. In this digital age, the child who learns to read deeply is not being left behind.

Like the Dap-ay that symbolizes unity and storytelling let us work together to motivate our children to reading and let them explore the wonders of literature.

References:

Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2019). PISA 2018 results (Volume 1). OECD Publishing

Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2023). PISA 2022 results (Volume 1). OECD Publishing

Department of Education. (2025). Functional Literacy Policy Brief (PB25-002). DepEd Bureau of Curriculum Development.